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Dynamic Simulation of Flare Gas Recovery System in the Case of Total Shut Down with Implement Case Study in South Pars

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Abstract

If the Flare Gases Recovery Systems (FGR) are used, then we can recover the wasted energy and prevent the emission of greenhouse gases like CO₂, SO_x and NO_x. In this paper, firstly, the steady state and dynamic simulation of the desired system was carried out through conducting the case study in energy region, Pars-Asalooyeh, Iran. The simulation results indicate that if the flare gas recovery system is used when one of the said refinery's phases has been out of order, the recovery of 142,000 SCMD of sweet natural gas, 594 (ton/day) of gas condensates and production of 297 (m³/hr) of H₂S would be possible. By following, performing dynamic simulation, the behavior of FGR system was studied when complete cessation of the system; Graphs are provided for changes in temperature, pressure and liquid level in the equipment of the FGR system.

Keywords: Refinery, Flare, FGRS, Simulation, Greenhouse Gases.

Introduction

Since the main energy dissipation in refineries happens in flare network and the highest level of environmental pollutants is released from this network, it is very important to optimize the performance of the network and investigate methods to recover the gases sent to flare. Due to burning gases in flare network, greenhouse gases such as CO₂, SO_x and NO_x are released to the atmosphere [1]. The contribution of Iran in global greenhouse gas emissions is 2.1% and Iran is the thirteenth largest country in the world in emission of greenhouse gas [2]. Now, five refineries are being operated in Pars-Asalooyeh Energy Zone and more than 365 MMSCF gas is burned per day in refineries flare network [3]. With the help of technological advancement in this field, now we can reduce the volume of burned gases in these refineries using a gas compression and recovery system. So, we can collect gases sent toward the flare network and re-use them as fuel gas in refinery and gas turbines [4].

Simulation of flare gas recovery system

FGR system is simulated in two steps. In first step, the system is simulated steady state, and the equipment specifications, the mass balance, the energy and a schematic of the process are obtained. In second step, the system is simulated dynamically and while one phase in refinery

system is out of service, changes are studied [5]. After steady state simulation, we can obtain the schematic for the process in which the mass balances and the energy is obvious. Figure 1 shows the PFD of FGR system. According to a study conducted by Shell, the capacity of simulated FGR unit is equal to 90% of the normal capacity of flaring in the refinery [6]. Since the recovered gases are used in fuel gas system of the refinery, the compressor outlet pressure is considered as 7 Barg.

Fig. 1. Schematic for the steady state simulation of process

Study on the dynamic simulation of FGR system at total shutdown

At total shutdown of one of phases in the refinery, according to the control logic for discharge of different units, all units in the phase are discharged within 36 minutes. The range of changes in gas flow rate sent to the flare network is from 140621(Kg/hr) to 535034 (Kg/hr). The change of the flow temperature is from 56 C⁰ to 72 C⁰ [7]. In dynamics simulation of the FGR system, the effect of changing the temperature of the gas sent to the flare network on the performance of the FGR system is studied at total shutdown and discharge of one phase. As the temperature of gases sent to FGR system increases, the operating condition is changed for two-phase separator at the compressor inlet. Figure 2 shows the changes in the condensate separation at separator before the compressor. Figure 3 also shows the changes in the gas separation in the separator.

Fig. 2. Graph of changes in the condensate separation

Fig. 3. Graph of changes in the gas separation

As the temperatures increases, the efficiency, and consequently the compression ratio, of the compressor is reduced. If the heat transfer in the intermediate and end coolers in the compressor is assumed to be constant during the dynamic changes, the temperature of the compressor outlet increases due to the increase in the temperature of the gas entering the compressor. Figure 4 shows the changes in temperature, pressure and flow rate at the compressor output while the temperature of the gas sent to the compressor is increased.

Fig. 4. Graph of changes in temperature, pressure and flow rate at the compressor

Due to temperature variations in the flow entering the three-phase separator, temperature and pressure in the separator are change greatly. The combination of the flow at the separator outlet has also variations. As the temperature of the gas discharging the compressor increases and the pressure decreases, the temperature and the pressure at the tree-phase separator show increasing and decreasing trends, respectively. Figure 5 shows the variations and Figure 6 also shows a decreasing trend in the amount of fluid gathered in the 3-phase separator as the temperature increases and the pressure decreases.

Due to changes in the three-phase separator, the input flow to the separation unit of sweetening system is increased. Figure 7 shows the changes in the flow rate of sweet gas and hydrogen sulfide separated in sweetening unit. It is clear that the flow rate has an increasing trend.

Fig. 5. The graph of variation of temperature and pressure

Fig. 6. Graph of changes amount of fluid gathered

Fig. 7. Graph of changes in flow rate of refinery fuel and hydrogen sulfide

Conclusions

In this paper we studied the steady state and dynamic simulation of the recovery system for the gas sent to the flare in a sample refinery. The steady state simulation results indicate that if the flare gas recovery system is used when one of the refinery's phases has been out of order, the recovery of 142,000 SCMD of sweet natural gas, 594 (ton/day) of gas condensates and production of 297 (m³/hr) of H₂S would be possible. Also, we studied the changes in the temperature of the gases sent to the flare during total shutdown of the refinery as well as the impact it had on FGR system behavior. The results are shown in separate graphs. It is obvious that the efficiency of the compressor is reduced due to the increase in the temperature of the gas sent to the flare network; therefore, the value of separation in two and three-phase separator shows a drastic change which is shown in the graphs.

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References

- [1] Trenberth K.E., Global Warming: It's happening, natural Science, Vol. 1, (1997).
- [2] Sekhavatjou M.S., Hosseini Alhashemi A., Daemolzeq E., Sardari A., Opportunities of GHGs Emission Minimization through Processes Improvement in Iranian Oil Industries, Energy Procedia, Vol. 4, (2011) 2104-2112.
- [3] Rahimpour M., Jamshidnejad Z., Jokar S.M., Karimi G., Ghorbani A., Mohammadi A.H., Comparative study of three different methods for flare gas recovery of Asalooeye Gas Refinery, Journal of Natural Gas Science and Engineering, (2012) 17-28.
- [4] GPA, Zero Flaring by Flare Gas Recovery, Environcomb Limited, AL KHOBAR, 29 November 2006.
- [5] Urban Z., Matzopoulos M., Marriott J., Applying Dynamic Model in Designing Safety System Can Reduce Capital costs, Hydrocarbon Processing, (2010) 41-47.
- [6] Allen G.D., Wey R.E., Chan H.H., Flare Gas Recovery in Shell Canadian Refineries, The fifth industrial energy technology conference, Houston, 1983.
- [7] Kang C.S., Kim T.O., Chang H.M., Operating Manual Utilities and offsites, DB-2017-140-P312-214, Hyundai, Iran, south Pars gas field, phase 4,5, 2004, pp. 145-151.